

1 **Intransitive competition is common across five major taxonomic groups and is driven by**
2 **productivity, competitive rank and functional traits.**

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31 **Running head:** Drivers of intransitive competition

32

33 **Summary**

34 **1.** Intransitive competition can be driven by multiple factors, including environmental
35 conditions, the functional traits of the species involved or the topology of competition networks.
36 Studies simultaneously analyzing these drivers are rare and therefore their effects on intransitive
37 competition are poorly understood. Additionally, organisms compete either directly or via
38 interference competition for resources or space, within a local neighbourhood or across the
39 habitat. Therefore, the drivers of competition could change accordingly and depend on the taxa
40 studied.

41 **2.** We performed the first multi-taxon study on pairwise competition across major taxonomic
42 groups, including experiments with vascular plants, mosses, saprobic fungi, aquatic protists and
43 soil bacteria. We evaluated the degree of intransitivity from the pairwise competition matrix
44 including all species and also for each possible three-species combination (triplets). We then
45 examined the effects of environmental conditions, competitive rank, and functional traits on
46 intransitive competition.

47 **3.** Intransitive competition prevailed in all taxa, but was less likely under fertile conditions.
48 Variance in competitive rank between species strongly reduced intransitivity, with triplets
49 composed of species differing widely in their competitive ranks much less likely to be
50 intransitive.

51 **4.** Including functional traits of the species involved more than doubled the variation explained
52 compared to models including competitive rank only. Both trait means and variance within
53 triplets affected the odds of them being intransitive. However the traits responsible and the
54 direction of trait effects varied widely between taxa, suggesting that traits can have a wide
55 variety of effects on competition.

56 **5. *Synthesis:*** Our study comprehensively evaluated the drivers of competition across multiple
57 taxa and showed that productivity and competitive rank are fundamental drivers of
58 intransitivity. In one of the first studies to do so, we showed that not only the functional traits
59 of each species, but also those of the accompanying species, determine competition
60 intransitivity. Our study shows that intransitive competition is widespread across multiple taxa
61 but can dampen under fertile conditions or for those species with large variance in their
62 competitive abilities. This provides a first step towards predicting the prevalence of intransitive
63 competition in natural communities.

64

65 **Key-words:** bacteria, bryophytes, competition hierarchy, coexistence, functional traits,
66 protists, rock-paper-scissors, saprobic fungi, vascular plants.

67 **Introduction**

68 The lack of competition hierarchy (intransitive competition) is the equivalent to the
69 rock-paper-scissors game in that no single species outcompetes all the others, and therefore
70 local extinctions are avoided (Gilpin 1975; Laird & Schamp 2006; Rojas-Echenique &
71 Allesina 2010). Intransitive competition can occur if there are reciprocal competitive
72 advantages. For example, a system could exhibit an intransitive loop if species A competes
73 more effectively for nutrients than species B ($A > B$), B outcompetes C ($B > C$), but C is able
74 to prevent resource uptake, reproduction or growth by species A through interference
75 competition, e.g. the production of allelochemicals ($C > A$; Aarsen 1992; Lankau & Strauss
76 2007; Gallien 2017). Intransitive competition is gaining attention as a potential mechanism
77 for species coexistence (Laird & Schamp 2006; Allesina & Levine 2011; Soliveres *et al.*
78 2015; Maynard *et al.* 2017a) and could also affect other important community and ecosystem
79 attributes such as spatial patterning, sensitivity to exotic invasions or diversity-function
80 relationships (Vandermeer & Yitbarek 2012, Henriksson *et al.* 2016, Maynard, Crowther &
81 Bradford 2017b).

82 In general, all taxa within a trophic level and with similar environmental preferences
83 will compete against each other for key resources directly (e.g. nutrient uptake) or indirectly
84 (e.g. allelopathic compounds), although the relative importance of resource or interference
85 competition can vary substantially between organisms. For example, mosses, intertidal
86 organisms or fungi might compete mostly for space and this competition can be dominated by
87 interference mechanisms, which individuals use to prevent overgrowth by others (Buss 1980;
88 Maynard *et al.* 2017a). Conversely, plants, protozoa or bacteria may compete more directly
89 for resources although sessile organisms do so more locally than mobile organisms.
90 Intransitivity in competition networks may decline in well-mixed communities (Reichenbach,
91 Mobilia & Frey 2007; Laird & Schamp 2015; Yitbarek & Vandermeer 2017) and therefore
92 could be less common for mobile taxa. Despite intransitive competition has been described in

93 many taxa (see reviews in Gallien 2017, Soliveres & Allan, in press), the wide range of ways
94 in which different organisms can compete has been seldom considered. The lack of studies
95 applying common methodologies across taxonomic groups, together with the different
96 prevailing modes of competition within each taxon, limits our capacity to evaluate the extent
97 of intransitive competition in nature, and to identify generalities in the factors driving it.

98 The degree of intransitivity observed in a community may also depend on
99 environmental conditions such as productivity or heterogeneity (Gilpin 1975; Allesina &
100 Levine 2011; Schreiber & Killingback 2013). However, empirical evidence for these
101 environmental effects remains rare (Dormann 2007; Bowker, Soliveres & Maestre 2010a;
102 Soliveres *et al.* 2015; Ulrich *et al.* in press). Productivity might reduce intransitivity through
103 two different mechanisms: i) for sessile organisms it might increase the asymmetry of
104 competition by causing a shift to light competition at high productivity, which would allow a
105 smaller number of species to monopolise limiting resources (e.g., DeMalach, Zaady &
106 Kadmon 2017), or ii) if it reduces the number of resources species compete for (e.g., Harpole
107 & Tilman 2007). Heterogeneity, in turn, can increase intransitivity by the opposite
108 mechanisms, reducing competitive hierarchies and allowing the species to compete for a
109 larger variety of resources (Allesina & Levine 2011; Schreiber & Killingback 2013).
110 However, a higher productivity could also increase the size of the species pool or the
111 importance of competition for community assembly, potentially increasing the role of
112 intransitive competition as driver of coexistence (Gilpin 1975; Bowker *et al.* 2010a).

113 In addition to the environment, the functional traits of the species competing are
114 important determinants of the outcome of pairwise competition (Schamp, Chau & Aarsen
115 2007; Kunstler *et al.* 2012; Herben & Goldberg 2014; Kraft, Godoy & Levine 2015).
116 According to the limiting similarity theory, species that differ in their functional traits should
117 also differ in their niches and therefore should compete less strongly with each other (e.g.,
118 Herben & Goldberg 2014). However, trait differences could also indicate strong differences in

119 competitive ability (fitness differences) between species and, in this case, competition would
120 be stronger between species with different trait values (Mayfield & Levine 2010; De Bello *et*
121 *al.* 2012). Strong intransitive competition arises from species reciprocally excluding each
122 other and could therefore be promoted by large differences in traits linked to competitive
123 ability for different resources. However, very heterogeneous competitive differences between
124 species pairs (i.e., large trait differences) can also destabilize intransitive networks (Gallien *et*
125 *al.* 2017), and thus trait differences could also be expected to reduce intransitivity. Functional
126 trait differences could therefore alter the degree of intransitivity in competition networks,
127 although this effect is poorly understood (Gallien 2017; Maynard *et al.* 2017a). In addition to
128 the effects of traits on intransitivity, the competitive rank of a species might affect its
129 likelihood of participating in an intransitive loop, as it has been hypothesized that intransitive
130 competition networks are nested, meaning that the dominant species form intransitive loops
131 but that hierarchical competition occurs between dominant and subdominant species
132 (Soliveres *et al.* 2015; see also Laird & Schamp in press). Despite the prominent role that
133 functional traits could have in determining intransitivity in competition networks; their effect
134 as drivers of competition intransitivity and whether this varies depending on environmental
135 conditions or between different taxa is unknown.

136 Here we explore the generality of intransitive competition in nature by combining re-
137 analyses of published (Carrara *et al.* 2015a; 2015b; Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2017; Maynard
138 *et al.* 2017a) and new pairwise competition experiments to explore the generality and
139 nestedness of intransitive competition in nature. These experiments include 124 species across
140 five different taxonomic groups: vascular plants, mosses, saprobic fungi, soil bacteria and
141 aquatic protists. For mosses and bacteria, we also analyzed how increasing productivity
142 affected the degree of intransitivity in the competition network. Finally, we examined the
143 effect of the functional traits of competing species as drivers of intransitive competition. Our
144 hypotheses were: i) intransitive competition is widespread across the taxa studied, but less

145 pronounced in mobile taxa such as protists and bacteria, ii) intransitive competition is reduced
146 (competition is more hierarchical) in more productive environments, iii) intransitive
147 competition prevails between dominant species, but not between the dominants and the rest of
148 species (i.e., intransitive competition networks are nested), iv) the functional traits of the
149 competing species influence the degree of intransitivity in their competition, and v) the
150 functional traits driving intransitive competition change under contrasting environmental
151 conditions and with the focal taxa.

152

153 **Materials and methods**

154 PAIRWISE COMPETITION EXPERIMENTS

155 Experimental designs and species numbers differed depending on the taxa studied; however,
156 all possible inter-specific pairwise combinations and monocultures were included for all taxa.

157 ***Vascular plants:*** seeds of 20 species (see species identities in Suppl. Table S1) were bought
158 from a commercial supplier (UFA Samen, Switzerland) and the seedlings were grown in
159 every possible pairwise combination for seven months (one replicate per combination). This
160 was done in 2 L pots filled with a mix of commercial soil (Ricoter, Aarberg, Switzerland) and
161 sand. After the seven months, the aboveground biomass was harvested for each species in
162 each pot.

163 ***Mosses:*** biomass samples were taken from 10 different species growing in grasslands of
164 southwestern Germany. Air-dried moss material (3 mg of each species) was used to start the
165 competition experiments: all pairs of species were replicated three times and were grown in 5
166 cm Petri dishes filled with commercial peat-based seedling substrate (Klasmann-Deilmann
167 GmbH, Germany; 80% peat, 20% coconut fibers; N 90mg/l, P2O5 100mg/l; K2O 250 mg/l,
168 buffered with CaCO₃ to pH 5.5). The Petri dishes were watered every second day until one
169 month after which mosses covered all the space in more than half of the Petri dishes (7

170 months in total). After this period, the cover of each moss species was estimated as a measure
171 of its abundance.

172 **Saprobic fungi (EU):** all pairwise combinations of thirty-one species of saprobic fungi from
173 Central Europe (hereafter EU fungi) were grown on potato dextrose agar in 9 cm Petri dishes.
174 To inoculate the fungi, previously sterilized and subsequently colonized poppy seeds (two
175 poppy seeds per plate) were used. After four weeks of growth at 22°C, the outcomes of each
176 pairwise competition were scored as draw (if no species overgrew the other or if mutual
177 intermingling without growth inhibition occurred), a win (if the target species overgrew its
178 enemy) or a loss (if the target species was overgrown).

179 **Saprobic fungi (US):** thirty-seven isolates from wood decay Basidiomycete fungi from North
180 American populations (hereafter US fungi) were grown in 10 cm Petri dishes filled with 2%
181 (w/v) malt extract agar. For each pairwise competition experiment, two competing species
182 were inoculated using three plugs placed at equal distances (see details in Maynard *et al.*
183 2017a). After eight weeks at 22 °C, competition was inferred from whether one species
184 overgrew the other or not.

185 **Protists:** every possible pairwise combination of a set of 10 protist and one rotifer species
186 (hereafter “protists” for simplicity) were grown in microcosms with 10 mL sterilized culture
187 medium and 0.45 g · L⁻¹ of protozoan pellets (Carolina Biological Supply, NC USA; 6
188 replicates per combination; see Altermatt *et al.*, 2015; Carrara *et al.* 2015a; Carrara *et al.*
189 2015b for further details). After 21 days at constant environmental conditions, the density of
190 each protist species within each pairwise combination and monoculture was recorded to infer
191 the outcome of competition.

192 **Bacteria:** strains from six terrestrial, dominant bacterial taxa were isolated from natural soil
193 (see Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2017 for details). Bacterial cultures were inoculated at equal
194 abundances in 10 g of two different soils (gamma-sterilized) and were grown in hermetic
195 containers for 8 weeks. Every pairwise combination was realized between these six bacterial

196 cultures only once, resulting in a total of 15 microcosms. After 8 weeks, the relative
197 abundance (number of gene copies \cdot g⁻¹ soil) of each bacterial strain was quantified using
198 qPCR.

199

200 MEASURING INTRANSITIVITY

201 In all cases, individuals of each species were either grown with a neighbor of their own (intra-
202 specific competition) or another (inter-specific competition) species. This allows a
203 comparison of the relative performance of each species in interspecific competition, after
204 accounting for differences in intrinsic growth rates, by using relative yields (RY; Keddy &
205 Shipley 1989; Grace *et al.* 1993; Dormann 2007): $RY_i = \text{performance of species } i \text{ growing}$
206 $\text{with species } j / \text{performance of species } i \text{ growing in monoculture}$. Our performance measures
207 were aboveground biomass (vascular plants), percentage cover (fungi, mosses) or abundance
208 (number of cells for protists, number of gene copies for bacteria) of each target species in
209 each possible pairwise combination. By converting these to relative yield we could generate a
210 species by species competition coefficient matrix. Cover was not estimated for the US
211 saprobic fungi, so instead of relative yields, interspecific competition was inferred from the
212 overgrowth data. For those pairwise competition experiments in which we had replicates
213 (mosses, protists and bacteria), the average value of each species across those replicates was
214 used to calculate relative yields. The competition coefficients within the matrix were
215 transformed to a binomial variable to obtain a single “winner” in each pairwise competition
216 trial (1 if $RY_i > RY_j$; 0 otherwise; where i and j are the species in the row and the column of
217 the matrix, respectively; see Suppl. Material S2 for a worked example). For the US fungi,
218 draws could also occur and these were scored as 0 for both sides of the matrix (i against j , and
219 j against i), so they did not influence our measure of (in)transitivity.

220 The transformation of RYs into a binomial variable allowed us to calculate the level of
221 intransitivity as the number of competitive reversals that occurred. To do this we first ordered

222 the terms within the matrix by row and column totals, so that most wins were concentrated in
223 the upper right corner of the matrix (see worked example in Suppl. Material S2). We then
224 calculated the degree of intransitivity as the number of competitive reversals ($RY_i < RY_j$)
225 which occurred (i.e. the number of 1s in the lower diagonal of the matrix Ulrich *et al.* 2014;
226 modified after Petraitis 1979; Laird & Schamp 2006). This metric therefore counts the
227 number of times that the species in the column (j) displaces the species in the row (i). The
228 number of reversals is likely to increase as more species (m) are considered (e.g., Grace,
229 Guntenspegen & Keough 1993). Thus, our metric is the normalized number of competition
230 reversals after accounting for all potential pairwise combinations, so that: $I = (2 \cdot (RY_i <$
231 $RY_j)) / (m \cdot (m-1))$, where zero/one values indicate completely transitive/intransitive
232 communities.

233 Converting the RYs to 1s and 0s removes any information on the strength of
234 competitive reversals and even a small difference in competitive ability counts as a win for
235 one of the species. This could lead to an overestimation of the degree of intransitivity if the
236 competitive reversals that occur are mostly just random changes in competitive ability
237 between similar species. This limitation is particularly important when pairwise competition
238 experiments are conducted without replication (such as in our vascular plants and fungi). To
239 address this issue, we calculated a new metric (*Inest*) based on the “nestedness” of the matrix,
240 which allows us to use all the information from the RYs (see Fig. S2b in Ulrich *et al.*, in
241 press). By using the RYs directly, we downweight competitive reversals that arise from small
242 competitive advantages in our estimation of intransitivity (e.g., $RY_j = 0.53 > RY_i = 0.47$,
243 would be weighted less than the case where $RY_j = 0.90 \gg RY_i = 0.10$). This metric also
244 requires re-ordering the species \times species competition matrix by row and column sums to
245 maximize the “wins” in the upper diagonal, but does not transform the RYs to 0s and 1s.
246 Instead, *Inest* calculates the difference between the RYs in the upper diagonal and those in the
247 lower diagonal (e.g., RY_{AB} vs RY_{BA} in the worked example in Suppl. Material S2, see also

248 Ulrich *et al.*, in press), weighting those differences by the distance of the position of a
249 particular RY to the diagonal of the matrix. Both metrics of intransitivity (*I* and *Inest*)
250 produced very similar results, although the strength of intransitivity was higher when using
251 the *Inest* metric based on continuous measures of competitive advantage (Suppl. Material S3).
252 We therefore focus on the use of *I* in the main text as it is more straightforward to understand,
253 more comparable with previous approaches and in fact more conservative in our case.

254 It has been argued that relative yields are not a good proxy of long-term competitive
255 outcomes or fitness differences between two competing species (Levine *et al.* 2017).
256 However, this important limitation seems only to occur in cases where the intra-specific
257 competition coefficient for one species in a pair is four or more times bigger than the other
258 (i.e. $\alpha_{ii} > 4\alpha_{jj}$), which did not occur in our experiments and may be relatively uncommon in
259 general (see full rationale and results in Suppl. Material S4). Relative yields based on biomass
260 (or related measures) were used here in order to have comparable metrics for all of our taxa.
261 However, it must be noted that, as with other metrics of biotic interactions (e.g., Holmgren,
262 Scheffer & Huston 1997), results can strongly depend on the performance measure used and
263 could be different if we had used survival, number of seeds or total extinctions as a measure
264 of competition displacement (see e.g., Carrara *et al.* 2015a, 2015b).

265 Our measure of intransitivity provides a single index for a community of any number of
266 species. However, single measures of competition intransitivity may fail to fully describe
267 these competitive networks (Laird & Schamp 2009; Alcántara, Pulgar & Rey 2017).
268 Therefore, to complement the community-level *I* metric, additional metrics based on three-
269 species combinations (hereafter triplets) were calculated. To calculate the triplet based
270 measures we scored each possible triplet as to whether it experienced competitive reversals
271 (i.e. $A < B < C < A$; rather than $A < B < C$ and $A < C$), this was done for all possible
272 combinations of three species within the community. There are only two possible states for
273 each triplet and each one was scored as fully hierarchical if there were no reversals and as

274 intransitive if there was a competitive reversal. The same approach was used to calculate
275 competitive reversals as for the whole community measures: i) RYs between the three species
276 pairs in the triplet were converted to 1 and 0s, ii) the matrix was ordered by row and column
277 totals, and iii) if after this re-ordering all the 1s were in the upper diagonal, then the triplet
278 was transitive, if not, then it was intransitive. Considering intransitivity in each triplet allowed
279 us to investigate the effects of the environment (i.e., productivity), the mean characteristics of
280 the species (i.e., competitive rank, functional traits) and the variation in species characteristics
281 (variance in competitive rank and functional traits) on intransitivity.

282

283 DRIVERS OF INTRANSITIVITY

284 *-Competitive rank*

285 Intransitive competition has been hypothesized to be nested, i.e., to occur within guilds of
286 competitively dominant or subordinate species, but not between these guilds (Soliveres *et al.*
287 2015). However, this hypothesis has not been tested experimentally. The nestedness of
288 intransitive competition networks was evaluated by measuring how the variance in
289 competitive rank of a triplet (which measures whether the triplet contains a mix of good and
290 poor competitors) affected its probability of being intransitive. Competitive ranks were
291 directly obtained from the pairwise competition matrix once it had been ordered by row and
292 column totals. After ordering, the species at the top are the strongest competitors (the ones
293 with more wins) whereas the species at the bottom of the matrix are the weaker competitors.
294 Therefore, the row number occupied by each species in the pairwise competition matrix is a
295 measure of its competitive rank (the smaller the row number, the stronger the competitor).
296 According to the nestedness hypothesis, species strongly differing in their competitive ranks
297 should not form intransitive loops. Thus, we expected that a high variability in competitive
298 ranks within a triplet would make it more likely to be transitive, while triplets consisting of
299 species similar in their competitive ability would have a higher chance of being intransitive.

300 The variability was measured as the non abundance-weighted mean pairwise distance (MPD)
301 of competitive rank across the three species.

302

303 ***-Functional traits***

304 Functional traits can be related to competitive ability, but can also offer additional
305 information on how species differentiate in the ways they compete (e.g., reciprocal
306 competitive advantages) and on how they respond to environmental changes. Thus, in
307 addition to the effects of competitive rank, the functional traits related to growth rate,
308 environmental tolerances or resource use were considered as potential drivers of intransitivity.
309 The average of each trait across the three species in a triplet was used to test if particular types
310 of species were more likely to participate in intransitive loops, and the MPD of each trait (non
311 abundance-weighted) within the triplet was used to assess if intransitivity was more or less
312 common between functionally different species.

313 Relative growth rate was available for all taxa and was calculated as the rate of
314 biomass (or cover) accumulation over a given period of time. This was obtained from the
315 monocultures for mosses, bacteria and protists, and from isolated individuals (growing
316 without competition) for the rest of taxa. Since all the species started with exactly the same
317 biomass (or cover), a single data point suffices to give an approximate measure of relative
318 growth rate. Since this is likely to be an important trait related to competitive ability, it was
319 included as a common predictor for all taxa. For vascular plants, height, specific leaf area,
320 seed mass, leaf dry matter content and leaf N content (obtained from the TRY database;
321 Kattge *et al.* 2011) were also included. These traits are linked to resource-use strategy and
322 competitive ability in plants (Schamp *et al.* 2007; Herben & Goldberg 2014; Reich 2014). For
323 mosses, colony type (three types depending on the degree of compaction: rough mat, smooth
324 mat and weft; from maximum to minimum colony compaction) and mean shoot length
325 (obtained from the Bryoatt database; Hill *et al.* 2007) were included in the analysis. Empirical

326 links between moss functional traits and competition have rarely been established, although
327 based on results for vascular plants and theory (Cornelissen *et al.* 2007), the traits we selected
328 should be important drivers of competition between mosses (Bowker, Maestre & Escolar
329 2010b). For the US fungi, traits related to chemical aggressiveness (hydrolytic enzymatic
330 activities), ability to overgrow other colonies (growth rate and density of the colony) and
331 nutrient uptake (wood decomposition, enzymes related to C and P cycling) were obtained for
332 published literature (Maynard *et al.* 2017a; see details in Suppl. Table S1). For soil bacteria,
333 enzymes related to their ability to capture P and degrade different sources of C were
334 considered in addition to growth rate (data from Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2017). Functional
335 traits for EU fungi were growth rate and phylum. For protists, invasibility (as estimated by
336 Mächler & Altermatt 2012) and functional group (small protists, large protists, mixotrophs;
337 Carrara *et al.* 2015a) were available. These traits are related to feeding guild, environmental
338 tolerances and growth rates.

339

340 ***-Environmental conditions***

341 The role of environmental conditions was evaluated in two of the taxa (mosses and
342 soil bacteria). For mosses, an N-fertilization treatment was added to our pairwise competition
343 experiment, which aimed to increase productivity and therefore affect the degree of
344 intransitivity (Gilpin 1975; Bowker *et al.* 2010a). Similarly, soil bacteria were cultivated in
345 two soils differing in their organic matter content and pH, which strongly affects the
346 abundance of the bacteria (e.g., Lauber *et al.* 2009; Maestre *et al.* 2015). The soils can
347 therefore be seen as representing different levels of productivity. Our experimental results
348 were compared with observational data from mosses growing in areas that differed in
349 productivity (Suppl. Material S5).

350

351

352 STATISTICAL ANALYSES

353 *-Analysis at the community level*

354 First, our six I metrics (one per group, with EU and US fungi analyzed separately as they used
355 slightly different approaches) were compared with 0 (values of $I = 0$ are related to perfect
356 competition hierarchy as no competitive reversals are observed in the community) using a t-
357 test. To examine the role of mobility in affecting the degree of intransitivity, the difference in
358 I between mobile (protists and bacteria) and sessile (vascular plants, mosses and fungi) taxa
359 was analyzed by means of a t-test.

360

361 *-Analysis including all 3-species combinations (triplets)*

362 *-Are intransitive competition networks nested?*

363 To test for nestedness in the intransitive networks we used the average competitive rank and
364 its mean pairwise distance (MPD) across the three species forming a triplet were considered
365 as predictors whether the triplet was intransitive. To analyse this, generalized linear models
366 with the logit link function were fitted for each taxon separately. MPD were calculated as the
367 presence/absence Rao's Q from the "FD" package in R (Laliberté *et al.* 2014).

368

369 *-Functional traits as drivers of intransitive competition:*

370 Functional traits are related to competitive ability, but also can offer additional information on
371 how species differentiate in the ways they compete (e.g., reciprocal competitive advantages)
372 and on how they respond to environmental changes. Thus, in addition to the effects of
373 competitive rank, the effects of functional traits related to growth rate, environmental
374 tolerances or resource use on intransitive competition were also considered. We were
375 interested in comparing the effect of mean traits with effects of the variability in such traits
376 between the competing species. Thus, the averages and MPD of the functional traits were
377 analyzed as predictors of the probability of a given triplet to be intransitive (using generalized

378 linear models with the logit link function). All traits and their MPD values were included in
379 our models, together with the average and MPD of competitive rank. In summary, we
380 evaluated sequentially four sets of models to analyse the triplets:

- 381 i) Intransitivity of each triplet (binomial variable) as the response to competitive rank,
- 382 ii) Intransitivity of each triplet (binomial variable) as the response to average and variance
383 (MPD) of competitive rank,
- 384 iii) Intransitivity of each triplet as the response to competitive rank and average trait values
385 across the three species, and
- 386 iv) Intransitivity of each triplet as the response to competitive rank, average trait values
387 across the three species and MPD for competitive rank and functional traits

388 We evaluated overall model fit by calculating Nagelkerke's pseudo- R^2 as implemented in
389 the function "RsqGLM" of the modEvA package in R. This allowed us to assess the extra
390 variation explained by the functional traits after considering competitive rank. In all cases, the
391 triplets within a species pool are not totally independent, as they may share one or two species
392 (e.g., ABC, ABD). To remove this pseudo-replication effect, p-values were calculated by
393 permutation, using 1000 permutations as implemented in the "PermTest" function of the
394 pgirmess package in R. For bacteria, the low number of possible triplets and the low variance
395 in the intransitivity levels of the triplets (only one was intransitive) prevented us from
396 including more than one predictor each time. Thus, we evaluated each predictor separately,
397 selecting the best (according to their pseudo- R^2 , see below) amongst the averages and
398 amongst the coefficients of variance.

399 In addition to these analyses, we evaluated the effect of functional traits as predictors
400 of competitive rank. This helped us to evaluate if the traits driving overall competitive ability
401 are the same ones driving the way species compete (intransitively or hierarchically).

402

403 *-Do the functional traits driving intransitive competition change with productivity?*

404 To test whether different traits drive intransitivity in productive environments, the
405 changes in intransitivity in the triplets of moss species competing under fertile vs control
406 conditions were analyzed using generalized linear models with a logit link function. In these
407 models, fertilization and its interactions with competitive rank and with the functional traits
408 were evaluated. Since no bacterial species were engaged in intransitive competition under
409 fertile conditions, only the data on moss species could be analyzed. All analyses were
410 performed using R version 3.0.2 (R Development Core Team 2013).

411

412 **Results**

413 HOW WIDESPREAD IS INTRANSITIVE COMPETITION?

414 All taxa studied, except the soil bacteria growing in rich soils, showed some degree of
415 intransitivity (Fig. 1). Our overall *I* metric, based on the proportion of competitive reversals in
416 the pairwise competition matrix, was significantly higher than 0 (pure hierarchical
417 competition): $t = 3.74$, $df = 5$, $P = 0.013$. Importantly, there was substantial variation in the
418 levels of intransitivity found across taxa, with very low values in fungi (US) and bacteria, and
419 much higher levels detected for mosses, vascular plants and protists (Fig. 1). In general, high
420 productivity reduced the degree of intransitivity in the communities, with declines detected in
421 both mosses and bacteria when growing under more fertile conditions, consistent with field
422 observations (Suppl. Material S5). These declines were consistent in both the community-
423 level *I* metric (bacteria and mosses; Fig. 1) and in the analyses focusing on the triplets
424 (fertilization effect in the glm for mosses: -5.91 ± 1.90 ; $P < 0.005$). We found no differences
425 in the level of intransitivity between sessile and mobile organisms neither at the community-
426 level ($t = 0.29$, $df = 4$, $P = 0.78$). The proportion of intransitive triplets out of the total number
427 of possible 3-species combinations ranged from 38.1% (mosses) to 0% (bacteria in fertile
428 soils; Fig. 1), with higher proportions observed for mosses, vascular plants (18.8%) and

429 protists (16.4%), consistent with the results found for the entire communities. These
430 proportions are similar to those previously reported for annual vascular plants (15-19% in
431 Godoy *et al.* 2017; 17-39% in Matias *et al.*, in press).

432

433 ARE INTRANSITIVE COMPETITION NETWORKS NESTED?

434 We found strong evidence that intransitive competition networks are nested, as intransitivity
435 was more frequent between species with similar competitive ranks. The coefficient of
436 variance in competitive rank had a strong negative effect on competition intransitivity in
437 vascular plants, fungi and protists, with a similar (non-significant) trend found in mosses and
438 bacteria (Fig. 2). The effects of mean competitive rank were less consistent: for the fungal
439 groups intransitivity was more common amongst dominant species (Fig. 2), whereas
440 intransitivity was more common amongst competitively weak species (higher ranks) in
441 mosses and was not affected by competitive rank in the rest of the taxa studied. .

442

443 DRIVERS OF INTRANSITIVE COMPETITION

444 Competitive ranks (average and mean pairwise distance [MPD]) explained, on average, 12%
445 of the variation in the probability of a triplet to be intransitive. This variation rose to 28%
446 when including functional traits. The increasing explanatory power when including functional
447 traits was due to both the average and the variance (MPD) in the functional traits of the
448 competing species (Fig. 3, see also Suppl. Material S6). In general, species with trait values
449 that indicate high competitive ability were less likely to be involved in intransitive
450 competition, these were tall vascular plants with low leaf dry matter content and high leaf N,
451 or fungi that grew faster (EU) or consumed more C (US; Fig. 3). While variance in
452 competitive ranks consistently decreased the probability of a given triplet to be intransitive,
453 trait differences did not have consistent effects. Triplets with high trait variance tended to be

454 less intransitive in vascular plants and protists, but not in fungi, mosses and bacteria (Fig. 3,
455 dashed columns).

456 Despite the strong effect of high productivity on intransitive competition, productivity
457 levels did not alter which functional traits affected intransitivity in mosses, where this could
458 be tested (no significant traits \times fertilization interactions were found). However, fertilization
459 did influence how competitive rank affected intransitivity in mosses, with the relationship
460 between moss average competitive rank and intransitivity shifting from negative in the control
461 to positive in the fertilization treatment (fertilization \times average competitive rank: 0.91 ± 0.35 ;
462 $P < 0.05$).

463

464 **Discussion**

465 INTRANSITIVE COMPETITION IS WIDESPREAD ACROSS DIFFERENT TAXA

466 Our results suggest that non-hierarchical competition is the norm, not the exception, in
467 ecological communities. We found evidence of non-hierarchical competition in all taxa
468 studied, adding to the increasing evidence for intransitive competition between vascular plant
469 species (Lankau & Strauss 2007), marine intertidal organisms (Buss 1980), biological soil
470 crusts (Bowker *et al.* 2010a), plankton (Huisman & Weissing 1999), bacteria (Kerr *et al.*
471 2002) and vertebrates (Synervo & Lively 1996). The apparent prevalence of intransitive
472 competition, across above- and belowground, terrestrial and aquatic communities, suggests
473 that a presumption of hierarchical competition in most current theories (e.g., Tilman 1982;
474 Chesson 2000) may need to be revised.

475 Our results contrast with other studies that have found fully hierarchical competition
476 (e.g., Grace *et al.* 1993 in vascular plants; Henriksson *et al.* 2016 in fishes; Friedman, Higgins
477 & Gore 2017 in bacteria). Further, in many other organisms (e.g., insects, birds, mammals)
478 where competition experiments are challenging, the possibility of intransitive competition has

479 hardly been considered. The variety of methods used to measure competition may contribute
480 to this lack of consensus. We used relative yields, calculated from species abundances, to
481 determine competitive outcomes. Relative yields could reflect reciprocal competitive
482 advantages and affect relative abundances of species and the functioning of communities
483 (e.g., Maynard *et al.* 2017b), but caution should be taken in using them as measures of the
484 long-term outcome of competition. Other methods for assessing competitive outcomes, based
485 on long-term survival have shown lower levels of intransitivity in competition networks (e.g.,
486 Carrara *et al.* 2015a, 2015b for protists or Godoy *et al.* 2016, Matias *et al.* in press for
487 vascular plants; but see Huismann & Weissing 1999; Kerr *et al.* 2002). In addition, whereas
488 some experiments have been performed under natural conditions, others keep environmental
489 conditions constant, and this reduction in heterogeneity under more controlled conditions is
490 likely to reduce niche differences and possibly intransitive competition. In general, the choice
491 of the performance measure and the experimental approach can have important implications
492 for how we perceive competition. Such issues are known in other areas where, for instance,
493 dryland plants can compete during the growth phase but still facilitate each other's survival
494 (Holmgren *et al.* 1997). This lack of agreement, and the knowledge gaps existing for many
495 taxa, emphasizes the need to better understand the conditions under which competition is
496 intransitive, how the degree of intransitivity in competition might change between life history
497 stages and how this impacts coexistence between species but also their abundances and
498 functioning. Multi-taxon studies using a consistent methodology to evaluate competition, such
499 as the one presented here, are a first step towards addressing this important research gap.

500

501 INTRANSITIVE COMPETITION IS DRIVEN BY SPECIES WITH SIMILAR 502 COMPETITIVE RANKS

503 We found that intransitive loops are more likely to occur between species similar in
504 competitive rank, which suggest that intransitive competition networks are nested (Soliveres

505 *et al.* 2015). This was true for protists, EU fungi and vascular plants, for which a higher
506 variability in the competitive rank of the species participating in a triplet negatively affected
507 the odds of such triplet to be intransitive. The mean rank of species in the triplet had positive,
508 neutral or negative effects on intransitivity depending on the group, meaning that intransitive
509 competition could prevail either between only dominant or only subordinate species,
510 depending on the taxonomic group in question. We hypothesize that intransitivity in general is
511 likely to be caused by trade-offs in competitive ability for different resources, or in resource
512 vs. interference competition, (e.g., C uptake vs aggressiveness; see also Maynard *et al.*
513 2017b). Assuming that functional traits were not only related only to competitive ranks, but
514 also to the different ways by which different species compete for resources (Kunstler *et al.*
515 2012; Kraft *et al.* 2015, see also Ulrich *et al.* in press, Saiz *et al.* in press, Suppl. Material S6),
516 this could explain the positive effects of trait variation in the intransitivity level of triplets of
517 fungi, mosses or bacteria (Fig. 3) even when the variance in competitive ranks had a negative
518 effect. However, when competing species are too different in their ranks (i.e. between
519 dominant and subdominant species), such reciprocal competitive advantages would not be
520 sufficient to reverse very large competitive ability differences. Recent theoretical work has
521 shown that where competitive ability differences are heterogeneous between pairs of species
522 (e.g. species A and B are much better competitors than C but C is only slightly better
523 competitor than A) the positive effects of intransitive competition on coexistence are reduced
524 (Gallien *et al.* 2017). As it may be unlikely that very large pairwise competitive ability
525 differences form intransitive loops, it may be more common for intransitive competitive
526 reversals to stabilize coexistence between species similar in competitive ability.

527

528 INTRANSITIVE COMPETITION IS DRIVEN BY THE ENVIRONMENT, THE WAY
529 SPECIES COMPETE AND THE FUNCTIONAL TRAITS OF THE TARGET AND
530 COMPETING SPECIES

531 The conditions under which competition is more likely to be intransitive have only been
532 explored in a handful of mathematical models (e.g., Allesina & Levine 2011; Schreiber &
533 Killingback 2013), and in empirical studies focusing on a single taxon (e.g., Bowker *et al.*
534 2010a; Soliveres *et al.* 2015; Maynard *et al.* 2017a). However, to our knowledge, no studies
535 have simultaneously studied these different drivers of competition intransitivity and how they
536 change according to the way different organisms compete.

537 We found that environmental conditions influenced the degree of intransitivity.
538 Specifically, increased productivity reduced the number of competitive reversals in mosses
539 and bacteria, which is consistent with results from field observations in vascular plants and
540 mosses (Soliveres *et al.* 2015; Suppl. Material S5). More fertile and productive conditions
541 could reduce the opportunities for intransitivity to emerge from reciprocal competitive
542 advantages by two different mechanisms: i) by reducing the number of resources species
543 compete for (Harpole & Tilman 2007), and therefore the potential for trade-offs in
544 competitive ability to lead to reversal, or ii) by increasing the asymmetry of competition, for
545 instance by shifting competition from nutrients to light (DeMalach *et al.* 2017), which would
546 also reduce intransitivity if large competitive ability differences are less likely to be reversed
547 (as proposed by the nestedness hypothesis). Our study also shows that intransitive
548 competition can shift from the dominant to the weak competitors under such productive
549 conditions (fertilized vs control mosses). This could be explained if dominant species
550 compete mainly for a single resource which makes competition more hierarchical and less
551 intransitive, whereas the remaining species need to fight for the leftovers using a variety of
552 competition strategies and therefore continue to compete intransitively. The relationship
553 between fertility and intransitive competition does not seem, however, to be monotonic. Field
554 observations (Bowker *et al.* 2010a) and theory (Gilpin 1975) suggest that an increase from
555 very low to moderate productivity levels may enhance intransitive competition by increasing
556 the species pool able to colonize a given site and the number of resources for which species

557 compete, both factors which should increase the chance that some species engage in
558 intransitive competition. To identify under which fertility levels intransitive competition is
559 maximized, and whether or not different taxa respond in the same way, is an exciting venue
560 for future research.

561 Three-species experiments (Kerr *et al.* 2002) and mathematical models (Reichenbach
562 *et al.* 2007; Laird & Schamp 2015; Yitbarek & Vandermeer 2017) suggest that intransitive
563 competition is less frequent in mobile taxa that compete in “global” neighbourhoods as
564 opposed to those that compete locally (sessile organisms). This is supported by the lack of
565 intransitive competition found in other manipulative experiments with organisms growing in
566 well-mixed environments, such as bacteria (Friedman *et al.* 2017), aquatic protists
567 (Vandermeer 1969), or necrophagous insects (Ulrich *et al.* 2014). Despite this, we found no
568 strong evidence for a reduction in intransitivity in mobile taxa, mainly due to the high level
569 observed in protists (but see Carrara *et al.* 2015a) and the moderate levels found in fungi.
570 Mobility can, in theory, allow species to take up resources at different points in space,
571 homogenizing resource distributions and preventing trade-offs in competitive ability for
572 different resources. It might also allow competitive species to avoid the influence of
573 allelopathic compounds, reducing the benefit-cost ratio of producing such toxins
574 (Reichenbach *et al.* 2007). In addition, mobility can allow species to escape competition in
575 well-mixed environments (Fronhofer *et al.* 2015) and can lead to greater opportunities for
576 niche differentiation. All these mechanisms could reduce the opportunity for intransitive
577 competition to stabilise coexistence, although we found little evidence to support this.

578 Another explanation for the taxon-dependent changes in intransitivity we found is the relative
579 size of the organism vs the habitat in which it was grown. Soil bacteria were grown in a larger
580 medium (relative to their size), and thus could more easily have avoided competition, perhaps
581 explaining the low prevalence of intransitive competition in these communities. Exploring

582 further the effect of mobility, local vs global competition mechanisms and the spatial scales at
583 which intransitivity emerges would allow a better understanding of its effects on coexistence.
584 Apart from mobility, size or competitive rank, we found some evidence that species with
585 traits more related to competitive ability in productive environments (tall plants with high
586 tissue nutrient levels and fast growing fungi) were less likely to engage in intransitive
587 competition. This parallels what we discussed above regarding productivity and reciprocal
588 competitive ability differences and suggests that species adapted to high productivity
589 environments may also be less likely to form intransitive loops. If functional traits of species
590 do affect their likelihood of engaging in intransitive competition then we might expect
591 changes in intransitivity to also feed-back to affect trait distributions. Previous studies have
592 shown an increase in functional trait diversity under intransitive competition (Maynard *et al.*
593 2017a, Ulrich *et al.*, in press), but these changes are not always expected (Gallien 2017). Our
594 results suggest that, if intransitive competition is driven by reciprocal competitive advantages
595 (as seems to be the cases for fungi, mosses and bacteria), then it should strongly relate to
596 functionally diverse communities. This is so because differences between species across
597 contrasting trait or resource use strategies can enhance such reciprocal competition (Herben &
598 Goldberg 2014; Ulrich *et al.* in press). However, in communities with strong fitness
599 differences, or driven by other mechanisms of competition, large trait differences could relate
600 to large fitness differences (e.g., Mayfield & Levine 2010, De Bello *et al.* 2012, Kraft *et al.*
601 2015) which, taken together with our results, suggest in turn that high intransitivity will relate
602 to low trait diversity. This is so because both simulations (Gallien 2017) and our results
603 suggest that too large fitness differences may dampen intransitivity, and if large fitness
604 differences are associated to large trait differences, then intransitive competition will be
605 linked to low trait diversity. In sum, the relationship between intransitive competition and
606 functional trait patterns seems to depend on the importance of reciprocal competition vs.

607 fitness differences as drivers of coexistence, and how the traits selected relate to these
608 competitive ability differences.

609 It must also be noted that the functional traits driving intransitivity were highly taxon-
610 dependent. Of course, this could be caused by the fact that we included different trait sets for
611 each taxon, according to data availability. However, even where we could use similar traits
612 across taxa, as in vascular plants, mosses and US fungi, the identity of the traits driving
613 competition intransitivity differed substantially. Similarly, the single trait that we had for all
614 our species (growth rate) had different effects depending on the organism. This lack of
615 common trait effects should be considered when applying trait-based approaches to find
616 general patterns across different groups of organism.

617

618 CONCLUSION

619 Using a multi-taxon experiment we found that fertility and competitive rank are generally
620 good predictors of intransitive competition. Intransitivity is common in less productive
621 environments, and between species that are similar in their competitive rank. We also showed
622 the need to be cautious when drawing general conclusions about competition and coexistence
623 from studies on single taxa. Finally, our results illustrate that not only the traits of the target
624 species alone, but the structure of trait values of all competing species is an important driver
625 of competition intransitivity. Our findings help to achieve a more predictive understanding of
626 which organisms and species may depend more on intransitive competition for their
627 coexistence, and also provide the first steps towards a more comprehensive theory on the
628 linkage between the role of the topology of competitor networks and diversity patterns in real
629 communities.

630

631

632

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660

661 **Data accessibility**

662 The data used in this article is available as Appendix S1.

663

664 **Author's contribution**

665 SS and EA designed the study, SS analyzed the data and wrote the first draft. All authors
666 contributed data and helped improving the text.

667

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838 **Supporting information**

839 Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article:

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842 **Figure 1.** Intransitivity levels across the taxa studied. Thick black dashes show the
 843 intransitivity level as calculated using the pairwise experimental approach with all the species.
 844 Dashed lines indicate the fertilizer treatment and the fertile soil for mosses and bacteria,
 845 respectively. To allow comparison between taxa, the intransitivity level of all possible
 846 combinations of 6 species (the minimum species number in the experiments) are shown (box-
 847 plots) for all the taxa but soil bacteria. The percentage of all possible 3-species combinations
 848 that were intransitive for each taxa are given in brackets (C = control, F = fertile conditions).

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852 **Figure 2.** Effect of the average and the variance (CV) of the competitive ranks of the species
 853 involved in a triplet on the probability of such triplet to be intransitive. Asterisks indicate
 854 significant differences according to the permutation tests performed to control for pseudo-
 855 replication when obtaining the *P*-values. Predictors for intransitivity in bacteria were tested
 856 one at a time, as only one triplet was intransitive.

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858 **Figure 3.** Effect of functional traits related to competitive ability (blue), resource acquisition
 859 (green) or other strategies (yellow; response to disturbances, trophic group) on the probability
 860 of each three-species combination to be intransitive. The effect (\pm standard error) of both the
 861 average (AV, filled bars) and the variance (calculated as the Mean Pairwise Distance [MPD];
 862 dashed bars) is shown. Asterisks indicate significant differences according to the permutation
 863 tests performed to control for pseudo-replication when obtaining the *P*-values.

864 **Supplementary Material for Soliveres *et al.*: “Intransitive competition prevails in five**
865 **different taxa and is driven by competitive rank and functional traits”**
866

867 Supplementary Material S1: Zip file with the matrices used for the community level analyses,
868 all the triplets obtained for each taxon, and each species information.
869

870 Supplementary Material S2: Worked example of the procedure followed to obtain the levels
871 of intransitivity from the pairwise competition experiments.....P2
872

873 Supplementary Material S3: Description and results when using *Inest*, an intransitivity metric
874 based on continuous and not binomial RYs.....P4
875

876 Supplementary Material S4: Analysis of the parameter space in which relative yields fail to
877 indicate competitive ranks.....P7
878

879 Supplementary Material S5: Description and results from field observations with mosses..P13
880

881 Supplementary Material S6: Relationship between functional traits and competitive ranks.P16

882 **Supplementary Material S2: Worked example of the procedure followed to obtain the**
 883 **levels of intransitivity from the pairwise competition experiments**

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887 This diagram show in 6 steps the methodology followed to calculate intransitivity levels in a
 888 given community from the relative yields obtained from pairwise competition experiments.

889 For simplicity, we focus only on two species (A and B), whose competitive coefficients are

890 highlighted in bold at every step. Step 5 corresponds to the sensitivity analyses reported in

891 Suppl. Material S4, and provides an intransitivity metric based on the difference (d) between

892 0.5 and each RY above the upper diagonal (RY > 0.5 is considered a "win", with higher RYs
893 indicating stronger wins). This difference between RY and 0.5 (d) is then multiplied by the
894 distance (L, number of cells between the target cell and the diagonal) between each RY and
895 the upper diagonal. The formula of *Inest*, therefore, is $Inest = 1 - ((2\sum_{i,j} d^2_{i,j}/L^2_{i,j}) / S(S-1))$,
896 where i = species in the row, j = species in the column, S = number of species, $d = RY_{i,j} - 0.5$
897 (for those competition coefficients lower than 0.5, as in the red quadrat in step 5 in the figure
898 above), and L = distance (number of cells) between position i,j and the diagonal (see Fig S2b
899 in Ulrich *et al.* in press). With this metric large competitive reversal contribute more than
900 small ones ($RY_{AB} = 0.10 \lllll RY_{BA} = 0.90$, instead of $RY_{AB} = 0.53 < RY_{BA} = 0.47$), unlike
901 the *I* metric presented in the main text, which counts all reversals equally, no matter the
902 difference between RY_{AB} and RY_{BA} . In the three species example there is a competitive
903 reversal (red number and arrow), and thus this 3-species combination would be considered an
904 intransitive triplet in the analyses focusing on 3-species combinations.

905

906

907 **Supplementary Material S3: Results when using *Inest*, an intransitivity metric based on**
908 **continuous and not binomial RYs**

909 We compare below the results obtained with *Inest* vs those obtained with *I* (the ones
910 presented in the main text).

911
912 **Figure S1.** Relationship between the intransitivity metric (*I*) based on binomial competitive
913 reversals ($RY_j > RY_i$), and the metric (*Inest*) based on the “concentration” of $RY > 0.5$ in the
914 upper diagonal. *Inest* is the average squared difference between the RY and 0.5 divided by the
915 distance of each RY to the matrix diagonal (see details in Ulrich *et al.*). The 1:1 line (dashed)
916 is shown to ease comparability. Those taxa without replicated pairwise competition
917 experiments are shown in blue. Notice that US fungi are not included in the analysis as *Inest*
918 could not be calculated from the data available. *Inest* and *I* are the inverse of τ_N and τ_C as
919 calculated from the formulas reported in Ulrich *et al.* 2014 and in press. Both metrics range
920 between 0 and 1, but their inverse ($Inest = 1 - \tau_N$ and $I = 1 - \tau_C$) provide more intuitive results
921 as higher levels of these metrics indicate higher levels of competition intransitivity.

923 **Figure S2.** Comparison of the effect of average and variance (CV) in competitive rank as
 924 drivers of competition intransitivity in 3-species combinations. Results using *Inest* are
 925 reported in the left side while those in the main text (using *I*) are reported in the right side to
 926 ease comparison. Notice that US.fungi are not reported as *Inest* could not be calculated for
 927 them. Differences in the drivers of intransitivity between one and the other approach are
 928 highlighted in red. * = significant difference at $P < 0.05$, estimated from permutations to
 929 avoid pseudo-replication in both cases.

930

931 **Figure S3.** Frequency histograms for the *Inest* values observed for all possible 3-species

932 combinations for each taxonomic group studied.

933 **Supplementary Material S4: Analysis of the parameter space in which relative yields fail**
934 **to indicate competitive ranks.**

935 It has been argued that relative yields (hereafter RY), the metric we used as a basis for our
936 analyses are not a good proxy of long-term competitive outcomes or competitive fitness
937 differences (Levine *et al.* 2017). The main issue is that relative yields indicate how a species
938 reduces the growth of its competitor (i.e., competitive effect) whereas stable coexistence may
939 depend more on how a given species responds to its competitors (i.e., competitive response;
940 see Supplementary Material in Levine *et al.* 2017 for full rationale and calculations). To
941 investigate the influence of this limitation in our results, we explored the parameter space in
942 which relative yields correctly or incorrectly predict fitness differences (the indicator of
943 competitive rank according to stable coexistence models).

944 Following the formulae used in Levine *et al.* 2017, we calculated fitness differences
945 between species i and k as: $\sqrt{(\alpha_{kk} \times \alpha_{ki}) / (\alpha_{ii} \times \alpha_{ik})}$, assuming equal intrinsic growth rates and
946 no niche differences. If this coefficient is higher than 1, then species i is the competitive
947 superior and will displace species k . Relative yield, in turn, was calculated as $RY_i = (1 + \alpha_{ii}) /$
948 $(1 + \alpha_{ik})$ for species i ; similarly, for species k : $RY_k = (1 + \alpha_{kk}) / (1 + \alpha_{ki})$. For relative yields to
949 correctly predict competitive rank RY_i should be higher than RY_k if the fitness differences
950 according to the formula above is higher than 1. Conversely, RY_k should be higher than RY_i if
951 fitness differences are below 1. Thus, only four competition coefficients suffice to calculate
952 RY and fitness differences (Levine *et al.* 2017).

953 Our analyses show that whether or not relative yields can predict competition rank
954 correctly depends largely on the ratio between the two intra-specific competition coefficients
955 (α_{kk} vs. α_{ii}), the ratio between the inter-specific competition coefficients (α_{ki} vs. α_{ik}) and the
956 ratio between intra- and inter-specific competition coefficients (α_{kk} vs. α_{ik}). Thus, we
957 simulated data altering these ratios, calculated relative yields and fitness differences, and

958 qualitatively assessed if relative yields predicted correctly competitive rank according to
959 fitness difference. Relative yields fail to predict competitive outcomes when intraspecific
960 competitive coefficients are substantially different (in the case of Levine *et al.*'s. 2017 model
961 $\alpha_{kk} = 10 \times \alpha_{ii}$), but they generally provide correct predictions when these intra-specific
962 competition coefficients are similar (in our simulations up to $\alpha_{kk} \geq 3 \times \alpha_{ii}$ Fig. S4). A re-
963 analysis of available data on plant competition (Godoy, Kraft & Levine 2014) shows that low
964 differences between intra-specific competition coefficients are very often the case in natural
965 communities (Fig. S5). We also show that the mismatch between RY and fitness differences
966 can be compensated by high differences between the inter-specific competition coefficients
967 (see blue section in the part below each panel in Fig. S4). If the ratio between inter-specific
968 competition coefficients ($\alpha_{ki} / \alpha_{ik}$) is larger than the ratio between intra-specific competition
969 coefficients ($\alpha_{kk} / \alpha_{ii}$), then the difference in RY is a good predictor of the fitness differences
970 between the species (diagonal dividing blue and red parts in Fig. S4). Overall, re-analyses of
971 the data from Godoy *et al.* (2014) suggests that the ratios between intra- and between inter-
972 specific competition coefficients are frequently close to 1 (Fig. S5), which indicates that RY
973 would generally be a good predictor of fitness differences in natural communities.

974 Lastly, we compared two scenarios, one in which intra- and inter-specific competition
975 are similar (Fig. S4) and one in which intra-specific competition is much larger than intra-
976 specific competition (as theoretically expected; Chesson 2000; Fig. Sb). For RY to correctly
977 predict fitness differences in the latter scenario, the ratio between inter-specific competition
978 coefficients has to be even larger than the ratio between intra-specific competition
979 coefficients. However, our re-analysis of Godoy *et al.* 2014 data (Fig. S5c) revealed that intra-
980 and inter-specific competition coefficients are frequently similar in size. Although we could
981 only evaluate the ratios between competition coefficients in real communities for vascular
982 plants, these results seem generalizable to other taxa. Indeed, competitive ranks in aquatic

983 protists were highly consistent whether using relative yields (from steady state data) or a
984 generalized Lotka-Volterra model to measure the competitive response (e.g., Carrara *et al.*
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986

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997

Ratio between intra and inter-specific competition (α_{ii}/α_{ki}) = 1

Ratio between intra and inter-specific competition (α_{ii}/α_{ki}) = 5

999 **Figure S4.** Results of the exploration of the parameter space in which relative yields correctly
 1000 predict competitive ranks according to fitness differences (blue) and where relative yields are
 1001 not good surrogates of competitive rank (red). The panel above shows the scenarios in which
 1002 intra- and interspecific competition coefficients were similar to each other, whereas the panel
 1003 below show the scenarios when the latter is much bigger.

1005

1006 **Figure S5.** Frequency histograms of the different ratios between intra-specific competition
 1007 coefficients (above), inter-specific competition coefficients (middle) and intra vs inter-
 1008 specific competition coefficients (below). In the two last cases, additional histograms
 1009 including only those ratios below 50 (middle) and 20 (below) are given to ease visualization.

1010 Data from Godoy, Kraft & Levine 2014.

1011

1012 **Supplementary Material S5: Description and results from field observations with**
1013 **bryophytes.**

1014 This study was conducted as part of the Biodiversity Exploratories project (Fischer *et al.*
1015 2010; www.biodiversity-exploratories.de) in the UNESCO Biosphere area Schwäbische Alb.
1016 This low mountain range is situated in southwestern Germany (48°20'60.0"–48°32'3.7" N;
1017 9°12'13.0"–9°34'48.9" E) and formed by calcareous bedrock. Mean annual precipitation of
1018 the study region ranges from 700 to 1,000 mm and mean annual temperature is 6–7°C. The
1019 grasslands in the study region harbor diverse vascular plant, bryophyte and lichen
1020 communities (Socher *et al.* 2013; Müller *et al.* 2014; Boch *et al.* 2016). In February 2015, we
1021 selected a subset of 29 plots (50 × 50 m) out of the Biodiversity Exploratories grassland plots,
1022 from which the moss material for the experiment described in the main text was obtained.
1023 Within each site, we established a 48-m long transect, along which 12 samples were taken at
1024 4m from each other ($N = 348$ samples). At each point, the cover of each bryophyte species
1025 was determined within a radius of 25 cm. Cover is strongly correlated with biomass in the
1026 studied mosses (Pearson's correlation, $r = 0.78$, $N = 147$; $P < 0.05$), and therefore was used as
1027 our surrogate of moss performance.

1028 For each site, and using the data from the 12 different points, we calculated the I
1029 metric using the methodology described in Ulrich *et al.* (2014). We calculated this metric for
1030 all species within each site, and also for the five dominant species. To analyze the effect of
1031 fertility on intransitive competition, we evaluated the relationship between I and overall
1032 bryophyte biomass, as an indicator of each site's fertility for bryophytes (Fig. S6).

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1037 **References**

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1063 **Figure S6.** Relationship between intransitivity and fertility, as indicated by bryophyte
 1064 biomass. Results of the quadratic regression, together with its confidence intervals (in blue)
 1065 are provided ($N = 29$). Intransitivity was calculated both for the five dominant species for
 1066 each of the 29 sites (black dots) or for all the species in the community (red dots). Notice that
 1067 intransitivity was generally higher across the dominant species, supporting results on the
 1068 effects of competitive rank in mosses shown in the manipulative experiment presented in the
 1069 main text.

1070

1071 **Supplementary Material S6: Relationship between functional traits and competitive**
1072 **ranks**

1073 We performed linear models with competitive rank as response and the functional traits
1074 included in Fig. 3 in the main text to evaluate how well the functional traits analyzed explain
1075 competitive ability. Traits were relatively good predictors of competitive rank, explaining
1076 between 14 and 60% of its variance (Table S6). However, this relationship was not strong
1077 enough to induce multicollinearity problems in the models presented in Fig. 3 in the main
1078 text, as the model coefficients obtained from the analyses in the main text were strongly
1079 related ($R^2 = 0.79 \pm 0.13$) from the same analyses but excluding relative growth rate (average
1080 and MPD) from the predictors.

1081 For three of the taxa, those traits that better explained competitive rank were also those
1082 influencing intransitive competition (highlighted in bold in the table below). However, in
1083 three of the taxa (mosses, protists and bacteria), the traits explaining competitive abilities
1084 (rank) did not match those explaining intransitivity.

1085

1086 **Table S6.** Summary results of the linear models evaluating the effect of functional traits as
1087 predictors of competitive ranks within each taxonomic group. We performed model
1088 reductions using the stepAIC functions and subsequently performing F-ratio tests.
1089 Highlighted in bold are those functional traits that were good predictors of both the
1090 competitive rank and the degree of intransitivity in the triplet. With the only exception of
1091 beta-glucosidase in the US fungi, both the average and the variance (RaoQ) in the highlighted
1092 traits were good predictors of the probability of a given 3-species combination to engage in
1093 intransitive competition.

Taxonomic group	Predictor	Coefficient±st.error	Adj. R²
Vascular plants	Leaf N	0.31±0.19	0.24

	LDMC	-62.3±24.4	
Mosses	Colony density: Weft	5.50±1.87	0.60
EU fungi	Phylum: Mucoromycotina	9.09±3.70	0.14
US fungi	beta_glucosidase beta_glucosaminidase	-4.70±2.23 6.34±1.48	0.31
Protists	No good predictor		
Bacteria	growth rate	-3.86E-10±1.70E-10	0.45

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